

COMPOSITION - DEPENDENT THERMODYNAMICS OF LAVES-TYPE $AB_{2\pm x}Hy$ HYDRIDES TAILORED USING STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

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Laves type AB_2 intermetallics belong to the most abundant group of intermetallic compounds containing over 1000 compounds. A large variety of the chemical nature of A (Mg, Ca, Ti, Zr, Rare Earth Metals) and B (V, Cr, Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Al) metals together with the existence of the extended solid solutions formed by mixing various selected components on both A and B sites dramatically extends the list of the known binary and ternary individual compounds. Equilibrium pressures in the systems of H_2 gas with the Laves type $AB_{2\pm x}$ intermetallics span a huge range of ten orders of magnitude (Figure 1) thus making this class of hydride-forming materials suitable for various applications including hydrogen getters, efficient hydrogen storage systems, thermally driven H_2 compressors [1].

Figure 1. Key applications of Lave type hydrides operating at various hydrogen pressures (10^{-8} - 100 bar H_2): low (getters), medium (hydrogen stores and metal hydride batteries) and high (metal hydride compressors).

Large volume of the accumulated experimental data motivates a need for establishing regularities in interrelation between the alloys compositions and corresponding hydrogenation properties. One viable approach applied in explaining the data and in predicting and optimizing the properties of the multicomponent hydrides [2] is based on the statistical analysis of the thermodynamic data. In the present study, the correlations were deduced by the applying a linear regression equation:

$$Y = A_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n A_i X_i \quad (1)$$
 where Y is a response parameter, X_i are the atomic fractions of the i -th component ($i=1..n-1$) considered separately for the A- and B-components, X_n is a deviation of B/A ratio from the AB_2 stoichiometry.

Applying Eq. 1 to the compositions of C14- and C15-type intermetallics (X_i) and thermodynamic properties of their interaction with H_2 (Y) showed satisfactory correlations between the calculated and reference data when the response parameter was taken as $Y = \Delta H^\circ / \Delta S^\circ$ ratio (temperature corresponding to the plateau pressure $P_0 = 1$ atm or $\sim 2/3$ of the critical temperature [3]), or as $Y = \Delta G^\circ = \Delta H^\circ - T \Delta S^\circ = RT \ln(P_0(T = 298 \text{ K}))$. Proposed approach allowed to identify several compositions of multi-component $AB_{2\pm x}$ intermetallics which show properties of advanced materials for hydrogen storage and compression suitable for applications.

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References

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